

A PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF A NEW XFEM FRAMEWORK FOR PREDICTING COMPLEX FRACTURE

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ABSTRACT

We provide a preliminary assessment of a new XFEM framework designed to capture the evolution of complex fracture and currently in development. Using four test cases, we demonstrate the ability of the proposed framework to capture self-intersection of a crack, the intersection of separate cracks, and bifurcation of a crack. For each case, the cracks are inserted and grown before the prediction of the displacement field by specifying the initiation point and the crack normal as a function of position. For each resulting crack state, we apply boundary conditions that demonstrate the ability of crack surfaces to freely separate, and predict and discuss the elastic response for each of those states. The new XFEM framework is shown to capture the expected displacement fields for the complex fracture states considered, providing a foundation for future studies.

1. INTRODUCTION

For decades, researchers have proposed methods for modeling the fracture of solids. A reliable methodology is to discretely model cracks by remeshing, ensuring sufficient mesh refinement around the crack and using special elements near the crack front due to the singularity. Though this method can accurately capture the effect of a crack with proper mesh refinement, remeshing can be difficult and expensive in general, especially in 3D. [1] When multiple cracks are allowed to coalesce, the description of the geometry of the crack surfaces, which is required by a meshing tool, becomes notably more complex since the intersections of crack surfaces must be accurately resolved. To circumvent the limitation of requiring the mesh to conform to discontinuities, Belytschko and Black extended the Partition of Unity Finite Element Method (PUFEM) of Melenk and Babuska to require minimal remeshing while predicting the propagation of a crack. [2] [3] This work led to the development of the extended Finite Element Method (XFEM). XFEM has been extensively used to model discontinuities without the need for remeshing by introducing enrichment functions, including a special set of functions to capture the singularity at the crack tip. [4] Though XFEM has the potential to provide accurate predictions, it remains computationally challenging to capture the interaction and coalescence of multiple crack fronts due to the stress singularity along the crack fronts.

To circumvent the stress singularity along the crack front, researchers have developed and extensively used cohesive zone models, which effectively smear the effect of the crack front across a finite area. A cohesive zone model aims to accurately predict the energy needed to propagate a crack and increases the tractability of the problem; however, the simplifying approximations do introduce notable error for the stress field near the crack front, since the singularity is not discretely captured. Despite the error introduced, cohesive zone models offer an efficient engineering approach to predicting the propagation of cracks, the progression of energy released, and the effect of crack growth on the far-field response. Consequently, cohesive zone models have been extensively used with the finite element method (FEM) to predict the

propagation of cracks along inter-element boundaries. This strategy is most convenient when the fracture is known to occur along material interfaces, such as the interlaminar interfaces of laminated composites, and has been used with great success. [5] Cohesive zone models can be used to predict fracture within a homogeneous material with FEM by inserting cohesive elements along inter-element boundaries. [6] However, this approach limits cracks to the boundaries of elements, making the solution inherently mesh-dependent, though extensive mesh refinement can mitigate the mesh dependency.

Leveraging the advantages of both XFEM and cohesive zone models, cohesive zones can be inserted within elements with arbitrary orientations that do not need to conform to a boundary of the element. This strategy involves using a set of enrichment functions to capture the displacement jump along the cohesive zone and assumes that the cohesive zone extends through the entirety of the element, removing the need for special enrichments at the crack front. This approach is sometimes referred to as the “cohesive segments method” and has been shown to be effective for mesh independent predictions of crack propagation. [7] Due to the robustness of the method, the cohesive segments method has also been implemented within commercial finite element analysis (FEA) software, such as Abaqus. [8] As with any XFEM approach, there are several strategies that can be used to account for the presence of the cohesive zone within an element. One typical technique is to subdivide the element for the purpose of integration, which is the approach originally used for the cohesive segments method in 2D. [9] In 3D, this approach is still possible, but it becomes more computationally expensive for curved surfaces. To ameliorate these issues, Endel Iarve proposed that the discontinuous Heaviside function be replaced with a regularized, smooth function within a higher order spline basis. [10] The approach, called the regularized extended finite element method (RXFEM), allowed the use of the original Gauss quadrature for integration of the stiffness of the element and contribution of the cohesive forces, removing the need to subdivide the element for integration. Later, the regularized Heaviside function was used within a classical FEM framework and successfully predicted the growth of intralaminar cracks in laminated composites. [11] However, the existing implementation of RXFEM in an FEA tool at the Air Force Research Lab called BSAM does not allow the enriched regions of cracks to overlap, preventing the coalescence of cracks.

The focus of this paper is to demonstrate new capabilities for predicting progressive fracture that capture the ability for cracks to arbitrarily grow, merge, bifurcate, and self-intersect. This research fits within a larger effort to reliably predict the progressive fracture where profuse cracking is expected, such as within complex 3D textiles or at the microscale in fiber/matrix ceramic-matrix composites. Currently, the limitations of existing methods and tools prevent the effective modelling of situations with profuse cracking, but this work uses a finite element framework under current development that is designed to provide such a tool. This paper considers several cases that demonstrate the ability of the method to capture the presence of some challenging crack paths within a material, including self-intersection of cracks, intersection of separate cracks, and bifurcation of a crack.

2. THEORY

This section provides an overview of the theory related to accounting for the discontinuities within the displacement field due to the presence of cracks and the method used to represent and track the crack during growth. Due to the scope and format of this paper, the discussion of the theory will be restricted to high-level concepts. However, a detailed discussion of the method used herein is warranted and is anticipated to appear in a forthcoming journal paper.

2.1 Overview of RXFEM

In RXFEM, when a crack extends through a previously uncracked element, the element is enriched to include twice the number of the degrees-of-freedom (DoFs), creating what he referred to as a “twinned”

element. In the implementation of RXFEM proposed by Endel Iarve, the element and nodes are duplicated, which is equivalent to the phantom-node method developed by Song et al. [12]. Consequently, this approach is convenient to implement into a classical FEA code. However, the same strategy can be conceptualized as introducing a new set of DoFs for the original element, which is the approach adopted in this work. In an element with two sets of DoFs, one set corresponds to the nodal displacements on the positive side of the crack, while the other set of DoFs corresponds to the nodal displacements on the negative side of the crack, with the sign taken from the signed normal of the crack. It should be noted that the corresponding locations for each set of nodal displacements in the element may span across both sides of the crack, with some of the nodal displacements representing the displacement at a position that is on the opposite side of the crack. Figure 1 provides an illustration of the RXFEM strategy for enriching a quadrilateral element, where \bar{u}_i^+ refers to the displacement vector at node i for the field on the positive side of the crack and \bar{u}_i^- refers to the displacement vector at node i for the negative side.

Figure 1. Illustration of RXFEM enrichment for a quadrilateral element

The existing shape functions can be used to interpolate each set of DoFs to a coordinate within the element as shown in Eqn. (1), where $\phi_i(\bar{x})$ is the i^{th} shape function evaluated at \bar{x} and N is the number of shape functions for the element:

$$\bar{u}^+(\bar{x}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \phi_i(\bar{x}) \bar{u}_i^+ \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{u}^-(\bar{x}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \phi_i(\bar{x}) \bar{u}_i^-$$

However, since both sets of DoFs correspond to fields that occupy the same space within the element, the displacement field within the cracked element can be calculated as a combination of both sets of DoFs as shown in Eqn. (2), where $H(x)$ is the Heaviside function that takes the value of 0 on the negative side of the crack and 1 on the positive side of the crack:

$$\bar{u}(\bar{x}) = H(\bar{x})\bar{u}^+(\bar{x}) + (1 - H(\bar{x}))\bar{u}^-(\bar{x}) \quad (2)$$

At this point, no regularization has been applied, and the model is equivalent to the phantom node method. As discussed in the previous section, cracks have been treated as either weak or strong discontinuities within the XFEM community, and both approaches have been employed with the cohesive segments method to capture the displacement jump that occurs along the cohesive surface as it opens. In RXFEM, cracks are modeled as weak discontinuities by replacing the discontinuous Heaviside function, $H(\bar{x})$, with a continuous approximation, $\tilde{H}(\bar{x})$, which is also referred to as a regularized Heaviside function. In the RXFEM implementation in a classical FEA framework proposed by Endel Iarve, the Heaviside function was regularized over the element intersected by the crack along with one extra element on each side of the crack. [13] This work will make the modification to regularize the Heaviside function over a single element (the element intersected by the crack), which requires a different regularization scheme. With this approach, \tilde{H} can only be one of three values at a node: 0 if the node is on the negative side of the crack, 1 if the node lies on the positive side of the crack, and 0.5 if the crack exactly crosses the node. At the quadrature points, \tilde{H} is calculated (a value in the range $[0,1]$) and stored. Replacing the Heaviside function in Eqn. (2) with the regularized Heaviside function, $\tilde{H}(\bar{x})$, the displacement field in the element could be recovered by a combination of \bar{u}^+ and \bar{u}^- weighted by $\tilde{H}(\bar{x})$, as given by Eqn. (3).

$$\bar{u}(\bar{x}) = \tilde{H}(\bar{x})\bar{u}^+(\bar{x}) + (1 - \tilde{H}(\bar{x}))\bar{u}^-(\bar{x}) \quad (3)$$

Many different regularization schemes can be conceived, and the different approaches should be evaluated in future work. However, in this study, we assume a simple (and effective) method to compute $\tilde{H}(\bar{x})$ at the quadrature points. If the signed distance function, $f(\bar{x})$, measures the distance from the crack surface to a point \bar{x} with the sign indicating which side of the crack the point lies, then the assumption is made that ratio of \tilde{H} to f can be interpolated from the nodes to the quadrature points, as shown in Eqn. (4), where the index i represents the node index within the element:

$$\frac{\tilde{H}(\bar{x})}{f(\bar{x})} = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \phi_i(\bar{x}) \frac{\tilde{H}(\bar{x}_i)}{f(\bar{x}_i)} \quad (4)$$

The value of \tilde{H} at the nodes can be expressed as a function of the sign of the signed distance function, as shown in Eqn. (5). Consequently, $\tilde{H}(\bar{x})$ for a location \bar{x} within the element can be rewritten as a function of exclusively the signed distance function evaluated at the nodes and location \bar{x} , as shown in Eqn. (6). The evaluation of the signed distance function requires a representation of the crack surface, which is discussed in the next section.

$$\tilde{H}(\bar{x}_i) = \frac{\text{sgn}(f(\bar{x}_i)) + 1}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{H}(\bar{x}) &= \frac{f(\bar{x})}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \phi_i(\bar{x}) \frac{\text{sgn}(f(\bar{x}_i)) + 1}{f(\bar{x}_i)} \\ &= \frac{f(\bar{x})}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \phi_i(\bar{x}) \left(\frac{1}{|f(\bar{x}_i)|} + \frac{1}{f(\bar{x}_i)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.2 Crack Representation

To track the location of the crack and allow the calculation of the signed distance function at the quadrature points and nodes, this work adopts a level-set method that explicitly evolves the representation of the crack surface, which means that the existing crack surface is not modified as the crack front grows. For explicitly evolving level-sets, Duan et al. recognized that there is a struggle between minimizing the error between the represented crack surface and the surface predicted by the fracture model and minimizing the discontinuity of an extension of the crack front with the existing crack surface. Consequently, Duan et al. proposed a method to find a level-set within an element that provides a least-squares minimization of the error with respect to the fracture model and the discontinuity. [14] The method introduces a weighting parameter that determines the relative importance of each of the two errors, and the authors recommended a value of 1 based on a parametric study. This work implements the same element-local level-set method and adopts the recommended value for the weighting parameter as proposed in [14].

If an element can only have one level-set value per a crack, then a crack can only enter the same element once, preventing crack self-intersection and bifurcation. This work modifies the level-set method by tracking each enrichment from each crack separately for each element in the mesh, allowing both multiple cracks to enter a single element, and a single crack to enter a single element multiple times. The algorithms developed to efficiently grow the level-set into the neighboring elements, while respecting that a crack cannot cross over other crack surfaces, and the algorithms for maintaining proper numbering of the degree-of-freedom are outside the scope of this paper; they will be documented in a forthcoming journal article.

2.3 Multiple Cracks

Though the Heaviside function is regularized over a finite distance, blending the \bar{u}^+ and \bar{u}^- fields through the cracked elements to yield the displacement field, there is still conceptually a field for each side of the crack. If a second crack were to grow into one of these two fields, \bar{u}^+ or \bar{u}^- , it could be accounted for in a very similar fashion to the first crack. For clarity, let the superscript indicate the crack and the sign of the field. For example, let \bar{u}^{1-} be the negative field for crack 1. If \bar{u}^{1-} is split by a second crack, then the field is separated into two parts again, \bar{u}^{2+} and \bar{u}^{2-} , but \bar{u}^{1-} can be recovered in the same way as \bar{u} can be recovered from \bar{u}^{1+} and \bar{u}^{1-} , as shown in Eqn. (7), where $\tilde{H}^2(\bar{x})$ refers to the regularized Heaviside function for the second crack.

$$\bar{u}^{1-}(\bar{x}) = \tilde{H}^2(\bar{x})\bar{u}^{2+}(\bar{x}) + (1 - \tilde{H}^2(\bar{x}))\bar{u}^{2-}(\bar{x}) \quad (7)$$

Eqn. (7) can be substituted into Eqn. (6) for $\bar{u}^{1-}(\bar{x})$ to yield \bar{u} as a function of \bar{u}^{2+} , \bar{u}^{2-} , and \bar{u}^{1+} , as shown in Eqn. (8), where $\tilde{H}^1(\bar{x})$ refers to the regularized Heaviside function for the first crack. The separation of the element into three displacement fields is illustrated in Figure 2, but it should be noted that each displacement field mathematically exists through the entire element (including the cross-hatched

region in the figure). The cross-hatched regions are shown to distinguish which part of the element the respective displacement field is trying to physically represent. Additionally, even though \bar{u}^{2+} and \bar{u}^{2-} exist throughout the element, their contribution to \bar{u} decays to 0 as \bar{x} approaches the top edge of the element due to the multiplication with \tilde{H}^1 and the restriction that \tilde{H}^1 is 1 along the top edge. For more cracks, the same concept can be applied to further (sub) divide the fields.

$$\bar{u}(\bar{x}) = \tilde{H}^1(\bar{x})\bar{u}^{1+}(\bar{x}) + (1 - \tilde{H}^1(\bar{x}))\left(\tilde{H}^2(\bar{x})\bar{u}^{2+}(\bar{x}) + (1 - \tilde{H}^2(\bar{x}))\bar{u}^{2-}(\bar{x})\right) \quad (8)$$

Figure 2. Illustration of enrichment for two cracks in a quadrilateral element

3. METHODS

This section presents the cases used to demonstrate the ability of the proposed XFEM method to capture challenging crack states. We consider four cases, with each case demonstrating a new capability over previous implementations of RXFEM. To create the crack states, cracks are initiated at specified locations and their growth is governed by a specified crack-normal that is purely a function of position. After the cracks finish growing, we apply boundary conditions and predict the elastic response of the model. The cases and boundary conditions were designed to be conceptually simple, and consequently, the correct displacement field can be intuitively known a priori. The material that the cracks grow through will be considered a homogeneous, isotropic material with a Young's modulus of 4 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.35, which is similar to the properties of a typical thermoset resin. The four cases considered in this paper are shown in Figure 3, with the final crack states and any specified boundary conditions (all other boundary

conditions are traction-free). For case 1, an $8 \times 8 \times 1$ grid with an extent along the x , y and z -axes of $[0, 1]$, $[0, 1]$ and $[0, 0.1]$, respectively, is used. All other cases use an $8 \times 8 \times 8$ grid with an extent along the x , y and z -axes of $[0, 1]$, $[0, 1]$ and $[0, 1]$, respectively.

It should be noted that visualizations show cracks extending through the entire element along intersections, since the level-set must extend through an entire element for the proposed method. However, it is important to recall from Section 2.3 that the regularized Heaviside function for the first crack reduces the influence the second intersecting crack from 1 to 0 across the element.

For this preliminary study, the displacement fields are shown and discussed. For a rigorous error analysis, mesh convergence should be assessed, the displacement fields should be carefully compared to a reference solution using conforming meshes, and the error in stress field should be explored. However, since this is a new framework and XFEM model, the infrastructure needed to conduct such a detailed study remains to be developed. Such a study must thus be reserved for a future work.

Figure 3. Crack paths and boundary conditions for considered cases (surfaces of FEA meshes are shown semi-transparently)

4. RESULTS

In this section, we present the displacement fields for each case shown in Figure 3 and provide a qualitative discussion of the results. Figures 4a and b show the y -component of the displacement, v , and the magnitude of the volume average stress in each element for the self-intersection case (case 1), respectively. Conceptually, there are two distinct regions for this case, each labeled in Figure 4a. Region 1 is the outer region of the rectangular domain that is cut by the self-intersecting crack. This region should experience a significant stress at locations near $x = 1$ and $y = 0.5$, and the region should freely separate along the crack surface. Region 2 is the inner region enclosed by the crack that is disconnected from the rest of the model, which should experience no displacement at all. Figure 4 shows that the method correctly captures the presence of the crack, allowing the crack surfaces to freely separate, and predicts a displacement and stress field that matches expectations for this case. It should be noted that the crack path was not directly specified as a function of the location. Instead, the crack was initiated, and the normal vector was specified such that a self-intersection would occur. The growth of the crack correctly stopped once it intersected itself. This demonstrates the ability of the model to not only capture the expected displacement field for this case, but also its ability to evolve a crack and correctly stop along regions of the front that intersects the cracks existing surface.

Figure 4. Results for self-intersection case (case 1)

Figure 5 shows two components of the displacement field and the volume average stress in each element for the case of intersecting orthogonal cracks (case 2). For this case, there are three separated regions of the model, each disconnected from each other by the cracks and labelled in Figure 5a. Since crack 2 separates region 1 and 2 and is orthogonal to the applied displacement, it is expected that the region 2 will experience no displacement, while region 1 experiences rigid body motion equal to the applied displacement at $y = 1$ along the y -axis. The proposed XFEM model correctly captures this behavior, as shown in Figure 5a, and as expected, predicts a zero stress in these regions, as shown in Figure 5c. Region 3 is separated from the rest of the model by crack 2 and experiences uniaxial tension along the y -axis. Analytically, region 1 should experience $w(z = 1) = -0.03$ and a uniaxial stress along the y -axis of $1e8$ Pa. The model captures both of these expected responses as shown in Figure 5b and c. It should be noted that part of the elements intersected by crack 1 should be stress-free, while another part should have an σ_{yy}

of $1e8$ Pa. Consequently, the volume average value of σ_{yy} is expected to be between 0 and $1e8$ for these elements.

Figure 5. Results for intersecting orthogonal cracks (case 2)

Figure 6a and b show the crack paths and the component of displacement along the z-axis, w , respectively, for the case of intersecting curved cracks (case 3). Again, there are three distinct regions bounded by the boundaries of the model and the crack surfaces, as labeled Figure 6a. The boundary conditions were chosen such that region 1 should experience rigid body motion of -0.1 along the z-axis, region 2 should experience no motion, and region 3 should experience rigid body motion of 0.1 along the z-axis. Figure 6b shows that the model captures this expected response.

Figure 6. Results for Case 3

When inserting the cracks for the case with the bifurcated crack (case 4), the first crack (denoted as crack 1) was initiated and specified to grow normal to the z -axis for any positions with $x > 0.6$, though the crack must completely cross an element in the proposed method. The second crack was initiated at $(0, 0, 0)$ and specified to grow with the normal, \hat{n} , expressed in Eqn. (9).

$$v(x) = (x - 0.6)\hat{i} + \hat{j}$$

$$\hat{n}(x, z) = \begin{cases} \hat{j} & x \leq 0.6 \\ -\hat{v}(x) & x > 0.6 \wedge z < 0.5 \\ \hat{v}(x) & x > 0.6 \wedge z > 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Again, the crack path was not directly specified, and bifurcation naturally occurred as a consequence of the growth algorithm, the normal vector, and the presence of crack 1. For this case, the planar crack (crack 1) and bifurcated crack (crack 2) create two distinct regions, which should freely separate. Figure 7 shows the displacement along the y -axis, which shows that the proposed model captures the expected displacement field for this case.

Figure 7. Results for the bifurcated crack case (case 4)

5. CONCLUSIONS

A new XFEM framework that provides new capabilities to established numerical tools used within the Air Force Research Laboratory was evaluated. The new method was shown to allow crack to merge with themselves and/or other cracks and bifurcate around other crack fronts. This preliminary study demonstrated the ability of the model to successfully capture the expected displacement fields for four cases, with each case demonstrating a challenging crack state. In addition, the ability of the proposed method to correctly evolve crack surfaces, correctly terminating growth where a crack front intersects an existing crack surface, was demonstrated for the four cases. These results illustrate that the proposed XFEM method could potentially capture complex fracture behaviors, such as those observed in 3D textiles and CMC's, and further evaluation and explanation of the algorithms involved will be part of future works as development of the framework continues.

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